

MONITORING AND ANALYSIS OF THE BEHAVIOR OF USERS OF COMPUTER SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *The issues of building effective software systems for protection against internal intrusions based on non-signature methods and having the properties of autonomy, adaptability and self-learning are considered. Separately, the problems of consolidating initial data from logs and OC protocols, methods of intermediate representation, data transmission and storage of collected data are considered. The architecture of the consolidation system and the workplace of a security analyst is proposed. Methods for using OLAP technology to analyze the collected data on user activity, as well as Data Mining algorithms for building a user behavior model based on association rules, are proposed. The constructed behavior model can be used to visually represent a security analyst in the form of a network of dependencies, as well as to automatically search for anomalies in user behavior and assess the degree of potential threat posed by each user. An experimental pilot version of such a system was implemented, which was verified according to the DARPA Intrusion Detection Evaluation Program method, using reference data sets. The results of experimental verification are given in the work. The issues of building effective software systems for protection against internal intrusions based on non-signature methods and having the properties of autonomy, adaptability and self-learning are considered. Separately, the problems of consolidating initial data from logs and OC protocols, methods of intermediate representation, data transmission and storage of collected data are considered.*

The architecture of the consolidation system and the workplace of a security analyst is proposed. Methods for using OLAP technology to analyze the collected data on user activity, as well as Data Mining algorithms for building a user behavior model based on association rules, are proposed. The constructed behavior model can be used to visually represent a security analyst in the form of a network of dependencies, as well as to automatically search for anomalies in user behavior and assess the degree of potential threat posed by each user. An experimental pilot version of such a system was implemented, which was verified according to the DARPA Intrusion Detection Evaluation Program method, using reference data sets. The results of experimental verification are given in the work.

Keywords: *DARPA, agents, consolidation system, text mining*

Introduction

The development and widespread introduction of information technologies, the increase in the volume and value of stored information leads to the need to protect it. The main security threat is intrusions into computer systems. An intrusion (or attack) on a computer system refers to any activity by a person or program that violates the integrity, confidentiality and/or availability of data. The greatest damage is caused by internal intrusions, since such an intrusion is carried out by a user (insider) who already has access to a computer system and may even be a legal user. records about events in the system with certain patterns - rules that describe attacks. Since the set of rules is fixed, such systems are dependent on the expert and are immune to new types of intrusions until the expert describes new rules. Such systems typically use the technique of periodically reviewing the audit and application logs (log files) collected by the system, however, the set of logs used by such systems is often quite limited, partly due to the need to develop different rules for each type of log. Today, it is important to create software technologies for building effective systems for protecting against internal intrusions based on non-signature methods [3, 4] and having the properties of autonomy, adaptability, and self-learning. Such protection systems should solve

the following tasks:

- collection and analysis of user and application work statistics;
- building and visualization of user behavior models;
- detection of anomalies in the work of users and software;
- identification of internal threats (from insiders)

Architecture

The system for monitoring and analyzing user behavior provides data collection, statistical reporting and data mining (Data Mining) of the collected data, namely: building associations and behavior patterns, searching for anomalies both within a separate computer system and within the network as a whole. The system is multi-agent. The data source is OS and software logs. The system consists of a consolidation server, collection agents, and an analyst workstation (Fig. 1). The initial data is read by the agent from computer system logs and consolidated on the server. Based on the collected data, statistical values are calculated and the data is analyzed. Statistical reports, found associations, built models and identified anomalies are transmitted to the analyst in the form of interactive dynamic reports. Analyst's workstation is a software module that ensures the user's work with the system. The following features are provided: management of consolidation (installation and configuration of agents), management of data analysis (data filtering, training of analysis algorithms, etc.), viewing reports by specified parameters.

The consolidation subsystem consists of two parts: the server part (consolidation server) and agents running on the computers from which the log file records are collected. There can be any number of agents. Agents can work on different platforms and collect information from different logs. The system allows you to add new agents or modify existing ones "on the fly" - without restarting the consolidation server. The agent contains local storage for intermediate buffering of collected data before sending, if this is implied by the data transfer configuration.

Agents

The agent collects information about events from various OS logs and software installed on the target computer. Transforms the collected records into a universal format developed on the basis of XML [5, 6, 7] and, according to the schedule, transfers the data to the consolidation server. The transfer of data collected by the agent can be carried out according to one of the following strategies. 1.Fixed volumes of data. The agent collects a certain amount of information or a fixed number of log entries and then sends them to the consolidation server. 2. Through equal intervals of time. The agent at regular intervals transfers all the data it has in the local storage, regardless of their volume. 3. According to the schedule. The agent transmits data only at the specified time. 4.Real time. The agent immediately transmits data on each newly read entry in the log. This strategy is the most resource-demanding. To ensure the distribution of the overhead costs incurred during the operation of the agent for reading and primary processing of log records, the mechanism of load sharing between the target computer and an additional computer allocated for converting data into a universal format can be used. The mechanism is based on the possibility of remote reading of some logs.

Consolidation Server

Upon receiving data from the agent, the consolidation server converts the records to an internal format and places them in storage. An important parameter of the storage and the consolidation system as a whole is performance. The storage load consists of the load of adding newly acquired log file data and the load of retrieving data for analysis. The nature of these actions is different. Data retrieval usually involves quickly getting all collected records for some time period, and this problem is solved by placing the records in sorted order by date. The situation is more complicated with the addition of newly received data, since one consolidation server must combine data from a large number of agents and even more log files. The average number of entries placed in the Windows log per unit of time can be estimated using the DARPA99 test [8]. Approximately

400,000 events per day, which is equivalent to approximately 10 events per second. For example, for a corporate network of 100 computers, the consolidation server must process and add to the store about 1000 events per second. Each entry in the Windows security log consists of approximately 20 parameters (meaningful features). Which results in 20000 parameters per second. Performance issues were resolved by dividing the storage files into three informational parts. The main parameters that are present in almost all records of all logs: event type, generation time, etc. Auxiliary parameters describing additional information about the event. Reference books for storing real values of both main and auxiliary parameters. The hashing mechanism is used to access the reference values. An event record from the log is divided between two files and reference files (Fig. 3): a file for storing identifiers of the main parameters, a file for storing identifiers of auxiliary parameters, and reference files. Reference files allow you to get their real values by parameter identifiers.

Saving data in files of main and auxiliary parameters, reference files allows in some cases to improve performance when accessing the storage. For example, if OLAP technology is used to analyze the collected data [8], then sometimes you can do without auxiliary parameters to fill in some facts in the data mart (Data Mart). Even if you have to access auxiliary parameters, it is not always necessary to get their actual values, sometimes just their identifier is enough. The structure of the specialized storage is shown in fig. 4. The storage is organized in the form of a tree, at the root of which are directories with a domain name, inside each directory with a domain name there are directories with the name of computers of this domain. Inside the directories with the computer name are files with collected log file records, divided by date, for example days. Reference files can be stored anywhere.

To illustrate the possibilities of statistical analysis of logged information using OLAP technology, let's consider a model example: building OLAP cubes based on the Windows OS registration log data. The following facts were

extracted from the Windows OS logs: logon; start processes; accessing files, folders and the registry. Based on the facts, OLAP cubes are built - multidimensional sets of values that reflect the statistics of user work. Facts are easy to determine by knowing the log event codes and the formats for presenting records of the desired event types. To build an OLAP cube [9], you should fill in the Data Mart - a relational database of a certain (like "star" or "snowflake") structure, which consists of a fact table and lookup tables. The facts in the Data Mart under construction are the revealed facts of activity in the system. And the available set of parameters for events [8] determines the maximum set of directories (OLAP measurements). So, for example, from the records of the security log for the facts of running processes (cube), dimensions are selected: the name of the running process, user, computer, parent process, etc. A hierarchy of computers has been introduced: domain - computer; hierarchy of users, hierarchy of time. Hierarchy in OLAP technology allows us to obtain the values we are interested in - OLAP measures both for an individual object or phenomenon, and for their group, which the hierarchy allows. The following parameters are defined for all types of events – OLAP dimensions and hierarchies: computers (Hierarchy: Domain > Computer); time (Hierarchy: Year > Month > Week > Day > Hour > ...); processes (Hierarchy: Computer > File name); parent processes (Hierarchy: Computer > File name); resources (Hierarchy: Computer > Path > File); resource types (without hierarchy: file extensions, etc.); login types (no hierarchy); operations (without hierarchy, for example, opening/closing a descriptor, stop/start processes, change rights, etc.); users (Hierarchy: Domain > User); completion status (no hierarchy). OLAP measures are those quantitative indicators that you want to get for certain facts by selecting the desired dimensions (log entry parameters) and hierarchy level. The following measures were chosen as the number of process launches, the duration of the process, the average duration of the processes. Generalization to all considered facts leads to the following OLAP measures: number of operations (counter); operating time

(sum) - between "pairs of operations" such as start/stop, opening-closing, etc.; number of operations per unit of time (calculated field).

	Login Types ▾		Processes ▾		Total
	☑ Console logon		☑ Network logon		
Users ▾	Login Facts	Count	Login Facts	Count	Login Facts
Administrator		17		7	7
alie		2			
ANONYMOUS LOGON				5	5
huws		1			
IUSR_HUME		7			
orionc		3			
triav		3			
Grand Total		33		12	12

Logon Cube Slicer Example OLAP technology can be applied to almost any type of OS and software logs. For example, facts and parameters can be extracted from the log of an anti-virus program. Build and fill Data Mart on them, build cubes. But OLAP technology allows you to build only statistical reports and does not solve the problem of identifying changes and their nature in the behavior of the system, applications and users.

Search for anomalies

The main idea of using anomaly detection methods is the assumption that the activity of the user of the system can be tracked and its mathematical model is built, which will allow detecting security policy violations and anomalies in user behavior. According to many experts in computer security, this approach is especially promising in the tasks of detecting internal intrusions, since it allows you to create the so-called "early warning" systems. The operating experience of internal intrusion detection systems shows that in most cases, an internal intrusion is immediately preceded by some anomalous (although possibly permitted) user behavior, i.e. Even before the attack or theft of information, the user begins to perform actions that are not typical for his previous activity or the activity of users of the same group (Fig. 7). A training set of log records is selected from the repository (usually records for a time period in which, in the opinion of the analyst, there were no intrusions). On the selected training set, the anomaly detection algorithm is "trained". The algorithm is then applied to newly arriving records, classifying them as normal or abnormal. If necessary, the analyst can

"train" the algorithm.

Scheme of using Data Mining methods to build user behavior models.

Maximum Rule Confidence:

$$P(x_i = a \mid x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_n) = \frac{\sum_j \text{confidence}(R_j(x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, a, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_n))}{\sum_{i,j} \text{confidence}(R_j(x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, a_i, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_n))}$$

Obviously, if the value of the i -th attribute matches the most expected value, i.e. the one that is predicted on the basis of the previously found associative model, then the confidence level of this attribute is 1, i.e. absolutely "expected" value. If such a value has not been encountered before at all, then its conditional probability will be equal to zero and the confidence level of the attribute will also be equal to zero, which corresponds to an absolutely "anomalous" value. In other cases, the confidence value will vary from 0 to 1, the smaller this value, the more anomalous the attribute value. The reliability of the entire event x in this case can

be defined as the product of the reliability of its attributes $Score(x) = \prod_i Score(x_i)$

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